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Children's University at Budapest University of Technology and Economics

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ABSTRACT

The very first edition of the Children's University summer camp intended to primary school students was organized in 2015 at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME). Since then, we held the summer camp every year. The concept of the Children's University was similar to that of several foreign initiatives but the camp was unique in its form and content.

Our aims were i) to show the 8-14 year old students -through colorful and diverting activities- the amazing richness of scientific fields covered by BME and ii) to stimulate their curiosity for natural sciences and technology. Our one week program consisted in lectures and seminars and was closed by a symbolic graduation ceremony. In addition, during the week children worked on projects in teams so that they could improve their cooperative skills.

At the end of the week a satisfaction survey was given to the parents and students to get their feedback on the camp. We summarize the results of the surveys taken in 2018.

The Children's camp was a challenge for the university staff as they got in contact with a much younger age group than usually.

BME students were responsible for taking care of the children during the program and guiding them between the places. The accompanying students were prepared for the task on a specific training.

With regard of the success of the Children's academy, we are now organizing satellite events with a point-gaining system during the whole academic year in order to sustain the interest.

1. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon that the interest of students is decreasing for the natural sciences, technology and technical sciences (STEM subjects) can be observed even in the developed countries [1,2]. Meanwhile, in the knowledge-based economy there is a growing need for STEM-skilled professionals [3]. The shortage of such professionals may be an obstacle for the economical development. The expert groups of the European Committee also deal in depth with these problems and are looking for solutions [4,5]. The insufficient supply of students eligible for higher education in the STEM field is closely related to the difficulties and eventual deficiencies of the high-school education. Often, the problem starts during the years of primary school [1], hence it is worthy to consider this group of age as well when searching for the solution. In many cases the high scientific standard of the curricula is frightening because it does not always take into account the age specificities. The present students are "digital natives", whose mentality, information processing mechanisms differ from those of former generations. It is widely accepted, that young children are not interested in natural sciences but in physical reality which can be perceived by their senses. In Western-Europe it is a long tradition that universities try to arouse the curiosity of children for natural sciences by organising events that popularise sciences in an age-appropriate manner [3].

Since 2015 in each year, the Budapest University of Technology and Economics organises summer schools entitled Children's University for children aged between 8 and 14 years. Though the idea was inspired by foreign initiatives, our program differs from them significantly.

2. Aim of the Children's University

Within the frame of the Children's University children gain insight into the life of the university, get acquainted with several disciplines in a playful manner and make experiments [6,7].

The goals of the Children's University:

- to familiarize children with different disciplines and scientific methods,
- to provide insight into to the function and rules of the university as well as to the everyday life of students,
- to present the possible choices for their future education,
- to raise the interest of children and improve their critical thinking,
- to create a link between children and university staff/students.

Our program is the result of the coordinated work of the whole BME community. Technical programs are realized by the teachers/researchers of the eight faculties but staff from the Central Library, Department of Physical Education and students' organisations participate, as well.

External partners including companies contribute largely to the success of the event in several ways: they offer financial support, but also organize visits or give talks where they provide context and role models.

2.1. Organisation of the program

The summer school is organized in two turns: the first one is intended for children aged between 8 and 10 years, the second one is for 11-14 year old children. In both turns 300 children participate, divided into 14 groups. The groups can be easily distinguished by the colour of their T-shirts. Each group has 3-4 adult mentors, who are responsible for the supervision, safety and comfort of the pupils and for their orientation among the different sites. Supervisors have the task to discuss with children about the scientific programs and university life as well. They are selected from volunteering BME students.

Once selected, they participate on a specific two day long training.

Participants receive a precise time schedule as *Table 1*. for the five days. The weekly program consists of lectures, seminars, leisure time and sport activities.

Table 1. The schedule for five days

	Monday	Tuesday		Wednesday		Thursday	Friday
7:30-8:00	Arrival	Arrival		Arrival		Arrival	Arrival
8:00-9:00							
9:00-10:00	Lecture	Lecture		Lecture		Lecture	Lecture
10:00-11:00	Leisure time	Seminar	Sport	Sport	Seminar	Leisure time	Leisure time
11:00-12:00	Lecture					Lecture	Lecture
12:00-13:30	Lunch	Lunch		Lunch		Lunch	Lunch
13:30-14:30	Seminar	Sport	Leisure time	Leisure time	Sport	Seminar	Project presentation, Graduation
14:30-15:30	Leisure time		Seminar	Seminar		Project	
15:30-16:30	Seminar	Seminar	Seminar	Seminar			
16:30-17:00	Departure	Departure		Departure		Departure	Departure

The mascot of the summer school is an owl, personified by a teacher of the university. As shown in. *Fig.1*. The Owl participates at the lectures, gives an introduction to the topic and helps the communication between the speaker and children.

Fig. 1. Owl with the pupils in the lecture room

2.2. Technical programs

The lecture and seminar topics cover a lot of different fields of science. The organisers put special emphasis to involve everything from the natural sciences, informatics and technical sciences to the economics and social sciences.

Some examples selected from the lectures and seminars are shown in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Some titles of lectures and seminars

Seminars	Lectures
Physics of medicine	The force of water
It's hard as a stone	Magical physics
Spaces of architecture	How our smart phone is produced?
Why is smart the smart phone?	Magic chemistry
Construction of electrical circuits	SMOG-1 student satellite
Chemhunting	Movement of animals
Do sport smartly!	Odo, the house of the future
Game with languages	Why the car is a computer?
How to bring down the Sun on the Earth?	Children's' rights in the world
Biosensors	Why is useful the economics?
Roaming in mathematics	About light and colours
Thunderbolts from a close view	What affairs are the monetary affairs?
How thick is a hairbreadth?	Magic molecules in the world of plants
Futuristic urban structures and utopias	The world of sons, sons of our world
Up-to-date energy use	Good or bad advertising
To do or not to do? The health begins in the mind.	On what and from what we build - roaming in geology
INTERNET of the things, or how the washing machine spies?	Sherlock Holmes and the science of the conclusion

Besides the presentation of the various colourful topics, there are activities where children themselves must create, mount or measure something, that is, they have to do manual work.

According to our experience, Children's University means a real challenge even for the experienced university staff as well, since they get in contact with a very different age group, so different educational methodology should be applied.

The project task ensures possibility for team work. Within the frame of the project the teams must find out, which product they would like to develop when they will be adult. The ideas must be shown during the graduation ceremony in a five minute presentation supplemented with graphical illustrations. Due to the live transmission, the parents may follow the event in another room.

At the end of each day, once the pupils have left, the organisers and the supervisors evaluate the daily experiences and discuss the expected events of the next day.

3. Feedback

At the end of the school both the children and their parents complete a satisfaction survey. The results of Children’s University 2018 is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of children satisfaction survey

	Question	average Turn 1	average Turn 2
1.	How would you mark the CU camp?*	4,79	4,56
2.	Did you find it useful?*	4,62	4,35
3.	How would you mark the work of the mentors?*	4,84	4,85
4.	Which lecture was you favorite?***	-	-
5.	Which seminar was you favorite?***	-	-
6.	Which sentence suits you best?****		
7.	Would you come again to CU?***	90%	81%
8.	Would you recommend CU to your firends?***	92%	82%
9.	Did you find new friends during CU?***	96%	95%
10.	Did you hear about the point gaining system of CU?***	69%	65%
11.	Comments	-	-

* average of answers on a 5-scale grade

** interesting that all lectures and seminars were mentioned

*** average of positive answers in percentage

**** Regarding interest in STEM, the children had to choose from the following answers:

Table 4. STEM interest of participating children

I became much more interested in STEM during CU.	56%	40%
STEM interests me and this did not changed.	38%	50%
I am interested in other areas than covered by CU.	6%	10%

Fig 2. Ratio of positive answers of participating children in Turn 1 and 2

Table 5. Results of parent satisfaction survey

	Question	average Turn 1	average Turn 2
1.	Where did you hear about CU?	-	-
2.	How much was the CU useful as a summer activity?*	4,93	4,85
3.	How much was your child satisfied with CU?*	4,80	4,71
4.	Does CU strengthened your child's interest in STEM?*	4,80	4,65
5.	How much was your child content after each days of CU?***	99%	98%
6.	How much did your child talk about his/her experience in CU*	4,19	4,31
7.	Did you child find new friendship during CU?***	81%	76%
8.	How much were you satisfied with the mentors?*	4,80	4,71
9.	How much are you satisfied with CU?*	4,88	4,80
10.	Would you bring your child to a CU in the next years?***	99%	94%
11.	Was the fee of CU acceptable?***	97%	98%
12.	Do you know the point gaining system of CU?***	90%	83%
13.	Comments	-	-

* average of answers on a 5-scale grade

*** average of positive answers in percentage

Fig 3. Ratio of positive answers of parents in Turn 1 and 2

Table 6. Results of mentors' survey

Question	average Turn 1	average Turn 2
How much are you satisfied with CU?*	4,37	4,44
Would you come again to CU as a mentor?***	85%	94%
How much were you tired during the days of CU?*	3,89	3,63
Did you find new relationships with mentors coming from different faculties?***	96%	100%
How much was the training useful?*	2,81	3,31

* average of answers on a 5-scale grade

** average of positive answers in percentage

The mentor students see the following strengths of CU:

	Total number of answers	Turn 1	Turn 2
university location	34	22	12
seminars	30	19	11
various themes	30	19	11
team, spirit	26	17	9
lectures	23	15	8
good organizing	19	11	8
project work	14	8	6
leisure activities	9	6	3

As can be seen from the answers above, the interest and success for the summer school is outstanding, both among the participants, their parents and the mentor students.

In order to give the possibility to a maximum number of children to enjoy the programs and to get closer to the world of science the selection of participants happens based on strict rules. Each applicant may participate only once in the summer school organized for younger children and once in the one for older children.

Due to the impressions obtained during the week, by the end of the school the children’s interest for the different disciplines is enormous. Most of them is willing to continue the school in spite of the fact that it is in summer holiday. This increased interest must be maintained and even strengthened regularly. Therefore the Children’s University does not consist merely of that one week in summer. We organize “sold-out” satellite events every month over the entire academic year. An example is the Children’s University Plus, where two lectures and experimental presentations are held. We regularly organize programs on Children’s Day and there is also the St. Nicholas Physics. Moreover, we joined the national programs of Everyone’s Physics and the Night of Researchers. The curiosity of these events is that the children are accompanied by family members or friends. The knowledge obtained together with an adult accompanying person can be further deepened. Besides, these occasions mean agreeable and entertaining family event.

4. Follow-up

Besides the stimulation of the children we would like to measure what programs arouse their interest to the largest extent. An informatical system was developed which allow to follow the attendance of our events. The children can collect points at the different programs (9 points for participating in a summer camp, 3 points for a mid-year event). For these points first a Silver Owl then a Gold Owl diplome can be obtained. The first Silver Owl diplomes was given in this academic year for six children. On the long term it will be interesting and instructive to see the ratio of

Children's University attendants choosing universities focusing on technology or natural sciences.

5. SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In Hungary, BME was the first institution to organize the Children's University in 2015, which was held in each year with great success since then. Mainly the children living in Budapest or in its agglomeration were able to benefit from it. For the participants several follow up programs are organised during the academic year such as Children's University Plus and St. Nicholas Physics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] OECD (2008), *Encouraging Student Interest in Science and Technology Studies*, OECD Publishing. doi: 10.1787/9789264040892-en.
- [2] Potvin, P., Hasni, A. (2014), Analysis of the decline in interest towards school science and technology from grades 5 through 11. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, **23**. 6. 784-802..
- [3] Joyce, A. (2014), Stimulating interest in STEM careers among students in Europe: Supporting career choice and giving a more realistic view of STEM at work. European Schoolnet, Brussels. In *3rd Education and Employers Taskforce Research Conference: Exploring School-to-Work Transitions in International Perspectives*. London, England.
- [4] Ulicna, D., & Royale, R. (2015), Does the EU need more STEM graduates?. Final Report, European Commission.
- [5] Council of the European Union (2010), *Council conclusions on increasing the level of basic skills in the context of European cooperation on schools for the 21st century* (HL C 323., 30.11.2010).
- [6] EUCU.NET (2010), *White Book*. European Children's Universities Network, Vienna.
- [7] Gary C., Dworsky C. (2013): Children's Universities—a "leading the way" approach to support the engagement of higher education institutions with and for children, *JCOM* **12**. 3. C03.